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STUDY OF ONE DIMENSIONAL CONDUCTION HEAT TRANSFER FOR CONSTANT THERMAL CONDUCTIVITY THROUGH COMPOSITE PLANE SLAB AND IN CYLINDER AT STEADY STATE CONDITION

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ABSTRACT

The present study is the observation of one dimensional conduction heat transfer through composite slab and in cylinder. Study carried out at steady state condition for constant thermal conductivity throughout the material. Boundary and initial conditions are set up to solve heat equation to obtain an Ansys generated simulation output of the heat conduction. The dimensions, temperatures and the convective heat transfer coefficient are entered in Ansys to generate the results. This software used to simulate interactions of all disciplines of physics, structural, vibration, fluid dynamics, heat transfer and electromagnetic for engineers. This study mainly focuses on how the variation of temperature and heat flux taking place throughout composite slab and in cylinder.

Key words: Heat transfer, Composite slab, Cylinder, Steady State, Thermal Conductivity, Heat Flux, Ansys etc

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1. INTRODUCTION

Conduction heat-transfer is the transfer of energy from the more energetic particles of a substance to the adjacent less energetic ones as result of interactions between the particles. There are two states of conduction, namely the steady state and the unsteady state conduction.

Steady state conduction is the form of conduction that happens when the temperature difference driving the conduction is constant, so that, the spatial distribution of temperatures in the conducting object does not change any further. In general, during any period in which temperatures are changing in time at any place within an object, the mode of thermal energy flow is termed transient conduction or unsteady state conduction. Heat is transmitted through the solids by the elastic vibrations of the atoms and molecules (crystal lattice vibration) and by free electrons (electronic thermal conduction). The transfer of heat by free electrons is very effective. The mechanism of electronic thermal conduction is like the electric conduction.

The term one-dimensional is applied to heat conduction problem when only one space coordinate is required to describe the temperature distribution within a heat conducting body, Edge effects are neglected, The flow of heat energy takes place along the coordinate measured normal to the surface. This paper aims to analyse the theory behind one-dimensional steady-state heat conduction in rectangular and cylindrically-shaped composite solids. This is first done by using theoretical equations (ideal conditions) and is then correlated with a numerical solution obtained as a result of simulations conducted in ANSYS. The quantities measured are the minimum and maximum heat fluxes, minimum and maximum temperatures, and the minimum and maximum directional heat fluxes for the composite rectangular slab and the composite cylindrical pipe.

2. EXPERIMENTAL METHODOLOGY

In a plane wall, the rate of heat transfer is as follows,

$$q = -kA \frac{\partial t}{\partial x} = kA \frac{t_1 - t_2}{x_2 - x_1} = kA \frac{t_1 - t_2}{\delta} = \frac{t_1 - t_2}{\frac{\delta}{kA}} = \frac{\Delta t}{R_k}$$

Where A is wall area perpendicular to the direction of heat flow and $R_k = \delta/kA$. We compare the above equation with the Ohm's law for an electric conductor, which is,

$$I = E/R = \frac{V_1 - V_2}{R}$$

The electric current I correspond to the heat flow q, the electrical potential E corresponds to the thermal potential, and the electrical resistance corresponds to resistance R_k to the heat conduction. Thus, the Fourier's equation of heat conduction is exactly analogous to the Ohm's law for an electrical conductor. This study used this electrical analogy frequently as it is quite useful in solving the complex heat conduction problems. The temperature difference Δt is the driving force for the flow of heat and $R_k = R = (\delta/kA)$ is the thermal resistance, which the wall offers to the flow of heat by conduction. The reciprocal of the thermal resistance is known as the thermal conductance of the wall.

Figure 1 Thermal circuit

Walls made of several layers of different materials are called composite walls. The composite wall consists of three layers of thicknesses δ_1 , δ_2 , and δ_3 .

Figure 2 Composite wall [8]

The thermal conductivities of these layers are k_1 , k_2 , and k_3 , respectively. The temperature of the outer layers of the wall is T_1 and T_4 as shown in the figure 2, with interface temperatures as T_2 and T_3 . It is being assumed that different layers are having perfect contact between them and hence the adjacent surfaces are at the same temperature. In the steady-state condition, the heat flow q is the same for all the layers and is constant. The equations of heat transfer through these layers are,

$$q = k_1 A \frac{T_1 - T_2}{\delta_1} \text{ for the first layer}$$

$$q = k_2 A \frac{T_2 - T_3}{\delta_2} \text{ for the second layer}$$

$$q = k_3 A \frac{T_3 - T_4}{\delta_3} \text{ for the third layer}$$

The temperature differences across the layers, from above equations, are

$$T_1 - T_2 = q \left(\frac{\delta_1}{k_1 A} \right)$$

$$T_2 - T_3 = q \left(\frac{\delta_2}{k_2 A} \right)$$

$$T_3 - T_4 = q \left(\frac{\delta_3}{k_3 A} \right)$$

In a composite wall, the rate of heat transfer is as follows,

$$q = \frac{T_1 - T_{n+1}}{\sum_{i=1}^n R_i} = \frac{T_1 - T_{n+1}}{\frac{1}{A} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\delta_i}{k_i}}$$

One frequently encountered problem is that of heat flow through the walls of a pipe or through the insulation placed around a pipe. Consider the cylinder shown in figure 3. The pipe is either insulated on the ends or is of sufficient length, L , that heat losses through the ends are negligible. Assume no heat sources within the wall of the tube. If $T_1 > T_2$, heat will flow outward, radially, from the inside radius, R_1 to the outside radius, R_2 the process will be described by the Fourier Law.

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Figure 3 Composite cylinder [8]

Similarly, in a cylindrical wall, the rate of heat transfer is as follows,

$$R = \frac{1}{2\pi kL} \ln\left(\frac{r_2}{r_1}\right)$$

Study will be analysing of the following examples using ANSYS.

Example 1. To find the heat flow rate through the composite wall, assuming one-dimensional flow.

$$k_A = 150 \text{ W/m}^\circ\text{C},$$

$$k_B = 30 \text{ W/m}^\circ\text{C},$$

$$k_C = 65 \text{ W/m}^\circ\text{C}, \text{ and}$$

$$k_D = 150 \text{ W/m}^\circ\text{C}$$

Figure 4 Example 1[8]

Example 2. A steel pipe having an ID of 2 cm, OD of 2.4 cm and thermal conductivity of the steel = 54 W/m-K carries hot water at 95°C. Heat transfer coefficient between the inner surface of a steel pipe and the hot water is 600 W/m²-K and the asbestos insulation with a thermal conductivity of 0.2 W/m-K and thickness 2 cm is put on the steel pipe. Heat is lost from the outer surface of the asbestos insulated pipe to the surrounding air at 30°C. Heat transfer coefficient from the outer surface to the surface of insulation is 8 W/m²-K. Determine the rate of heat transfer per length along the length of pipe. Also, determine the temperature of the inner and outer surface of the cylinder [8].

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Results and Discussion of Example One

First of all, make the geometry of the composite slab in the geometry section in ANSYS. Then define the material according to the example under the model section shown in figure 5 and figure 6. Then give input conditions that are the temperature of the surfaces.

Figure 5 Modelling of composite slab

Figure 6 Analysis of slab in ANSYS

We can see that the pattern of the flow is not stable, as there are four different materials with different properties used. As B had the least conductivity of all four materials, we can see from the graph that heat flux through B is minimum while through A and D is maximum. As from the above simulation, heat flux can be calculated as that minimum is 71737 W/m^2 and the maximum heat flux is $1.8088 \times 10^5 \text{ W/m}^2$ and the average heat flux is $1.303 \times 10^5 \text{ W/m}^2$ shown in figure 7.

Figure 6 Variation of maximum and minimum heat fluxes in the composite slab

The input temperature to the surfaces A and D was 400°C and 60°C respectively. So, It is clearly seen that linear pattern of the temperature change along the slab. The pattern is not observed linear when there is external force acting on it like convection or thermal radiation. While here only the temperature is the affecting the slab, we see that the minimum temperature is 60°C and the maximum temperature is 400°C with a linear pattern of flow. The temperature goes on decreasing as we move from the surface A to the surface D. The flow is as shown in the figure 8.

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Figure 7 Calculation of minimum and maximum temperatures in the composite slab

The directional heat flux varies material to material. The directional heat flux is highest in the material with highest conductivity and is lowest in the material with lowest conductivity. As from the calculation from the simulation from figure 9, the minimum directional heat flux is $-1.704 \times 10^5 \text{ W/m}^2$ in the material B and the maximum directional heat flux is -71730 W/m^2 in material A. Here the negative sign indicates the direction of the heat flux flow which is opposite to the conventional axes' direction.

Figure 8 Calculation of minimum and maximum directional heat fluxes in composite slab

3.2. Results and Discussion of Example Two

In this study first of all made the geometry of the composite cylinder in the design workspace. It is shown in the figure 10 and 11. Then in the model section, assign the values of temperature, convection coefficient and other parameters as specified in the example 2.

Figure 9 Modelling of composite cylinder

Figure 10 Analysis of cylinder in ANSYS

After that mesh the geometry in the model section and then give the input parameters, and then run the calculations and it can be clearly seen that as hot water was flowing from the middle of the cylinder, we observe that the highest total heat flux is at the interior part of the cylinder. While the cylinder was in contact with air on its surface, the least total heat flux is seen on the surface of the cylinder. The total heat flux goes on decreasing as we move from the centre of the cylinder towards the surface. The heat flux value is as denoted in the above figure 12. The minimum value of heat flux is 217.62 W/m^2 and the maximum value is 749.89 W/m^2 .

Figure 11 Variation of maximum and minimum heat fluxes in the cylinder

As hot water is flowing through middle of the cylinder, there the highest temperature is observed. On the surface as cylinder was in contact with air, there the minimum temperature is noticed. As we move from the centre of the cylinder towards the surface the temperature goes on decreasing. As denoted in the above figure 13. The calculated minimum temperature of the cylinder is 58.255°C and the maximum temperature is 93.794°C .

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Figure 12 Variation of maximum and minimum temperatures in the cylinder

The minimum directional heat flux is observed at the middle of the cylinder and the maximum heat flux value is obtained at the surface of the cylinder. The calculated minimum directional heat flux is -738.8 W/m^2 that is in the negative Z direction and the maximum directional heat flux is 731.8 W/m^2 that is in the conventional Z direction shown in figure 14.

Figure 13 Variation of maximum and minimum directional heat fluxes in the cylinder

4. CONCLUSIONS

Present study is carried out to check variation of heat flux and temperature in composite slab and in cylinder. Study involves three major assumptions, i.e. (i) One dimensional heat flow (ii) Constant thermal conductivity though out metal and (iii) Steady state heat transfer. The major conclusions of this study are as follows

- Composite slab have variation of temperature from 60°C to 400°C with a linear pattern of flow and heat flux from 71737 W/m^2 to $1.8088 \times 10^5 \text{ W/m}^2$ and the average heat flux is $1.303 \times 10^5 \text{ W/m}^2$.
- Cylinder has variation of temperature from 58.255°C to 93.794°C and heat flux from 217.62 W/m^2 to 749.89 W/m^2 .

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